

Journal of Composites and Compounds

A review of carbon nanotube/TiO₂ composite prepared via sol-gel method

Leila Bazli ^a, Mostafa Siavashi ^{b*}, Arman Shiravi ^c

^a School of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran, Iran

^b Christian-Albrechts-University Kiel, Faculty of Engineering, Kaiserstraße 2, 24143 Kiel, Germany

^c Department of Chemical Engineering, Amirkabir University of Technology, Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

A substantial review is performed in this work about the development and design of Carbon Nanotubes/Titanium Oxide nanocomposites. The fundamental method of sol-gel synthesis of Carbon Nanotubes is also reported here. Single-Walled and Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes are reviewed here as well. Finally, different applications for this nanocomposite are discussed.

©2019 JCC Research Group.

Peer review under responsibility of JCC Research Group.

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Article history:

Received 11 September 2019

Received in revised form 22 September 2019

Accepted 25 October 2019

Keywords:

Carbon nanotube

TiO₂

Nanoparticles

Nanocomposites

Characterization

Table of contents

1. Introduction	1
2. SWNTs and MWNTs	2
3. Methods of preparation	2
4. Sol-gel processing	2
5. TiO ₂	3
6. TiO ₂ -CNT nanocomposites	3
7. CNT/TiO ₂ preparation method	3
8. Applications	3
8.1. Photocatalysis	3
8.2. Biosensor	5
8.3. Solar cells	5
8.4. Antibacterial	5
8.5. Other applications	5
9. Conclusions and future insights	6

1. Introduction

Carbon and its compounds are an important part of nature [4-6]. Familiarity with diamond and graphite, which are infinite periodic networks of solid carbon, gets back to ancient times. Recently, the discovery of the nanotubes, fullerenes, and graphene have attracted the attention of researchers [7-10]. Meanwhile, there are many research concentrating on carbon nanotubes (CNT), which can be considered as a cylinder created by curling a graphene sheet having a regular hexagon structure.

CNT diameter can be several times smaller than its length [11].

A carbon nanotube was discovered by Iijima (1991) [12]. An ideal carbon nanotube has a hollow, seamless, tube-like structure and it consists of a hexagon carbon atom which is rolled by a slice layer of graphite surfaces [13]. Based on the number of graphite surface layers, they can be categorized as (I) single-walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) and (II) multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) [14]. CNTs can be considered as ideal catalyst carriers due to nanoscale hollow tube property, significant specific surface area, unique electronic structure, good absorbability, and remarkable chemical stability [15, 16]. In addition, it

* Corresponding author: Mostafa Siavashi; E-mail: stu213298@mail.uni-kiel.de

DOR: 20.1001.1.26765837.2019.1.1.1.0

<https://doi.org/10.29252/jcc.1.1.1>

This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

is reported that carbon nanotubes can be used as a support to disperse functional materials to improve their additional properties such as conductivity, structure, activity, and surface area [17].

Besides, CNTs exhibit a micro-range electric connection with a lower amount of additives due to their high aspect ratio making them a promising additive for LIB electrodes. In this regard, numerous reports have implied that the rate and cycling performance of composite electrode materials with CNT additives have been enhanced [18-20]. Note that the surface chemistry of CNTs allows them to be functionalized for especial applications.

Due to the abovementioned properties, CNTs have generated considerable interest in various applications such as polymer reinforcements, electronics, sensors, catalysis gas storage, and energy storage materials [21]. There are also many publications reporting the synthesis process, characterization, and their usage in various applications [22].

2. SWNTs and MWNTs

As mentioned, CNTs can be divided into two main categories: SWNTs (one graphene sheet) and MWNTs (several graphene sheets). Both are similar, but MWCNTs consist of several concentric tubes, in which they are fitted inside each other. Generally, SWNTs and MWNTs have diameters of 0.7–2 nm and 2–100 nm, respectively, while their length can be several millimetres to micrometres [23].

As MWCNTs possess large surface area and mesoporous characteristics as well as chemical stability, they may be a good alternative for catalyst and photocatalyst materials [2–5].

The usage of MWCNTs is based on the combination of advantageous properties of individual SWCNTs including their mechanical, thermal, optical, and electrical characteristics. It is noteworthy that the differences between the structural features of SWCNTs and MWCNTs influence dispersion and solubility in the solutions [24]. In addition, SWNTs are better fillers than MWNTs due to 1) Higher surface area and aspect ratio of SWNTs that provides more interfacial bonding over MWNTs and 2) The diameter of MWNTs outer shells can bond with the matrix and the inner shells diameter can slide and rotate freely, which is held only by Vander Waals forces. However, the drawback is that MWNTs are easiest to synthesize and process in large scale. Fig.1 and Table 1 illustrate the properties and structure of SWCNTs and MWCNTs, respectively.

Recently, nanocomposites based on MWCNTs have attracted much attention due to their one-dimensional ideal molecular structure, strong adsorption capacities, high surface areas ($>150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), good mechanical properties, chemical, and thermal stability as well as a dispersant of catalysts effectively [25, 26], enhanced electronic properties and a large capacity of electron-storage [27]. They are conductive with almost no resistance at room temperature [28].

In nanocomposites, $\text{TiO}_2/\text{MWCNTs}$ for instance, MWCNTs would accept photon-excited electrons or mixtures as the reservoir of electrons

Table 1.

Properties of SWCNTs and MWCNTs.

Properties	SWCNTs	MWCNTs
Specific Area (m^2/g)	400-900	200-400
Specific gravity (g/cm^3)	0.8-1.3	1.8-2.6
Tensile Strength (Pa)	$(3-50) \times 10^{10}$	$(1-15) \times 10^{10}$
Young's modulus (Pa)	1000	1000
Electrical conductivity (S/cm)	10^2-10^6	10^3-10^5
Thermal stability ($^\circ\text{C}$)	550-650	550-650
Thermal conductivity ($\text{W}/\text{m}^*\text{K}$)	3000-6000	2000-3000

and then transfer electrons rapidly that result in the prevention of the recombination of electron-hole pairs to produce more oxidants and radicals [29]. Considering all these, MWCNTs show the potential of increasing the activity of photocatalysis [30, 31].

3. Methods of preparation

Composites based on CNTs/ TiO_2 have been synthesized by various methods such as sol-gel [11], mechanical combination of TiO_2 , and CNTs [32], electrophoretic deposition [33], chemical vapor deposition [34] and electro-spinning [35]. However, some of these routes take a lot of time and are costly, and need higher pressure and temperature or multiple steps during the synthesis process [36, 37]. The electro-spinning and chemical vapor deposition techniques are almost hard to perform and need specific instrument so that quantifying the ratio between composite and compounds may get hard. Based on the preparation method, different physical properties and uniformity of the oxide coating would be obtained in the composite materials [3].

Compared with the other techniques, the sol-gel method is a low-cost [38-40] and facile strategy [41] to prepare various corresponding hybrid semiconductors. The sol-gel methods have been well developed, and various extended sol-gel techniques have been presented due to the controllability of the synthesis conditions and simplicity of this method [42, 43].

4. Sol-gel processing

Due to various advantages of sol-gel method, it can be used to prepare nanocomposites such as CNT/ TiO_2 [44]. In order to produce a highly crystalline anatase structure of oxide from its amorphous form, a high-temperature thermal treatment is needed. The high temperature leads to serious changes in the surface structure and particle size that can lead to a collapse of the mesoporous structure [45]. Thus mild conditions are required to synthesize TiO_2/CNT nanocomposites.

The sol-gel process could be divided into two major steps, namely, organic and inorganic. The organic route is used for functionalization of CNTs while the other is used for known surfactants to disperse CNTs [46].

During the sol-gel method, a suspension of the CNTs and precursors is provided, which leads to effective dispersion and molecular interaction between them. Furthermore, during the gelification process, the composite materials are formed at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which inhibits the initial dispersed state of CNTs. In addition, the sol-gel matrix contains many pores that are capable of encapsulating the metal nanoparticles [47], carbon nanotubes [48-53], and guest molecules [46, 54-56].

Sol-gel method provides the possibility of adding carbon nanotubes into the precursor carbide during the synthesis process that causes better connections between the carbon and nanotubes. Also, it provides a more uniform mesoporosity throughout the material [57].

Fig. 1. Structures of SWCNTs and DWCNTs (2 wall).

Fig. 2. Schematic of preparation of TiO₂-MWCNTs.

5. TiO₂

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is a photocatalyst known as an environmental-friendly component because of its great thermal and chemical stability, catalytic activity, strong oxidizing power, nontoxicity, low cost, and other outstanding properties [58, 59]. In addition, due to high redox potential, wide bandgap semiconductor, this photocatalyst has been studied during the past few years. The most important application of TiO₂ is in the decontamination of polluted waters with dyes from industries such as cosmetics and textile [60-62]. However, the activity of this material is low that limited its application. In addition, because of its high recombination ability and low quantum yield of photo-generated electron-hole pairs, it is poorly efficient [3, 17, 63, 64].

Therefore, in order to enhance its photocatalytic efficiency, various techniques have been proposed. Meanwhile, nano-architected TiO₂ provides superior characteristics namely large specific surface area, excellent biocompatibility, and high uniformity [65, 66], and it has been applied in various fields like fuel cells [67, 68], hydrogen sensor [69-72], biosensors [73-77], and highly efficient photocatalysis [78-80].

According to previous research, MWCNTs have the potential of enhancing the TiO₂ photocatalytic efficiency because they act as a photosensitizer and expand the absorption band of photocatalysts to the range of visible spectrum [81, 82]. Studies on MWCNTs /TiO₂ composites have revealed that they can enhance the photocatalytic degradation activities of organic-based contaminants as well as dyes [17, 83] and NO_x oxidation [84] under UV irradiation [30].

6. TiO₂-CNT nanocomposites

As mentioned above, the nanocomposites of TiO₂ have attracted great attention due to their superiority concerning physical, thermal, chemical, mechanical, optical, and electrical applications [85, 86]. Fig. 2 shows the procedure of CNT/TiO₂ preparation [3].

The production of CNTs/TiO₂ nanocomposite enables the utilization of the advantages of both materials including adsorption capacities of CNT with the surface area of 200–400 m²/g, reduction of E_g after doping of TiO₂ with CNT, as well as photocatalytic activity of TiO₂. The synthesis of CNTs with TiO₂ leads to easier control of morphology. Thus, these materials are activated via visible light radiation, yet the corresponding mechanism of activity in visible light is implicit. Two mechanisms have been proved to play a role in the addition of CNT to TiO₂ particles. One is the change of the sensitization and bandgap energy of TiO₂ while the other corresponds to the action of CNT as the photosensitizer, which is related to the permission of a reduction process and transferring electrons into the conduction band of TiO₂. The combination of nano-scale

TiO₂ with CNTs may improve the electron-hole charges separation due to irradiation [87].

Moreover, the resultant CNT with positive charge eliminates an electron from the TiO₂ valence band, and subsequently, the TiO₂ with a positive charge can participate in oxidation procedure as water in the formation of hydroxyl [12]. The carbon nanotube, coupled with TiO₂, can improve the overall performance of the photocatalytic process through a synergistic effect. Studies on CNTs/TiO₂ nanocomposites have been carried out by researchers in the field of the treatment of contaminated air and water using heterogeneous photocatalysis [88-90], photo-reduction of CO₂ [91, 92], hydrogen evolution [93, 94], sensors devices [95] and dye-sensitized solar cells [96-98].

The TiO₂-MWCNTs nanocomposite with hetero-junction microstructure (NCs) exhibits a great capability in conducting electrons and adsorption of organic pollutants [99, 100]. Additionally, due to the unique morphology of MWCNTs, which are composed of multiple overlaid graphite layers, form a tubular-shaped conductive structure through which the separation of electron-hole pairs on the surface of TiO₂-MWCNTs NCs is facilitated [64].

The mass ratio of CNTs/TiO₂ and the temperature of calcination are considered to be among the most effective parameters on the activity of CNT/TiO₂ composites. In this regard, the mass ratio in the range of 1.5–20 % is reported optimum for CNT/TiO₂, which is based on the value of treated pollutants.

Carbon nanotubes are considered as a good additive to TiO₂ photocatalysts because of their unique physical and chemical characteristics, particularly high surface area, and electronic conductivity. The high electronic conductivity of the carbon halts hole-electron annihilation on the surface of titanium dioxide crystals, resulting in the increment of the catalysis effectiveness [11].

The synthesis of CNT/TiO₂ nanocomposite has attracted much attention in the studies due to its high potential application in fields such as renewable energy and enhanced photo-activated catalysis being used in solar cells, sensor devices photocatalysis, CO₂ photoreduction, hydrogen evolution, and photo-electro-catalysis [93, 96, 101].

TiO₂/CNT composites are synthesized using sol-gel, chemical vapor deposition, and hydrothermal method. Scientists prefer sol-gel methods even though the methods can cause random agglomeration of TiO₂ onto the surface of nanotubes, a heterogeneous of CNTs by TiO₂, non-uniform coating, showing pure carbon nanotube surfaces. The photocatalytic activity of CNT/TiO₂ composites synthesized by the hydrothermal method is lower than the ones synthesized by sol-gel methods [87].

7. CNT/TiO₂ preparation method

CNT/TiO₂ nanocomposite has attracted the attention of researchers due to the decontamination of water and air by hydrogen evolution, heterogeneous photo-catalysis, dye-sensitized solar cells, and CO₂ photo-reduction. These composites have been prepared by various methods that uniformity of the physical properties and oxide coating of the composite materials are different based on the process of preparation. Sol-gel route usually results in the formation of a non-uniform coating and heterogeneous of CNT/TiO₂ nanocomposite that is showing random aggregation of TiO₂ onto the CNT surface due to bare carbon nanotube surfaces [102].

8. Applications

8.1. Photocatalysis

Nowadays, the depletion of fossil resources and serious water pollution are among worldwide concerns yet to be solved. The most favour-

Fig. 3. The schematic process of the elimination of pollution in water with photocatalyst.

able approaches for the remediation of wastewater are solar energy driving semiconductor photocatalysis; however, their practical use is limited because of the relatively low photocatalytic efficiency. To tackle this limitation, a variety of techniques have been proposed to produce advanced photocatalysts including the preparation of a composite catalyst consisting of semiconductors with various functional components such as atoms, individual semiconductors or metals that can lead to designing high-efficiency catalysts through a facile approach [103]. The schematic of pollution removal with photocatalyst is shown in Fig. 3.

Carbon nanotubes have many distinctive properties and are vastly used as a support material for many catalysts [103]. The applications of CNTs/TiO₂ photocatalysts have been studied by several researchers [84, 104]. Mechanism of photocatalytic degradation illustrated in Fig. 4.

Abd Hamid et al. [3] synthesized a MWCNT/TiO₂ with the modified sol-gel method. They studied the photocatalytic activity by photodegradation of reactive black 5 dye with ultraviolet light irradiation. Their result showed that the photocatalytic performance was improved significantly due to the high surface area of MWCNTs. This prevented electron-hole pair recombination.

Tseng et al. [105] investigated TiO₂/MWCNT nanocomposite with the aim of the relation between acid pretreated and photocatalytic activity. Their results indicated that the photodegradation efficiency increases 10% with increasing acid pretreatment time. In addition, they reported that the optimal acid pretreatments time was 4h that proved the important role of acid pretreatment time on physicochemical properties.

In other work, Chen et al. [17] studied the MWCNT/TiO₂ composite. They observed that the removal of methylene blue by composite under UV irradiation is not only due to photocatalytic degradation of TiO₂ and MWCNT absorption property. The electron transfer between TiO₂ and MWCNTs affected removal efficiency.

Yang et al. [106] prepared a TiO₂/CNT with different CNT content by sol-gel process and hydrothermal treatment and investigated the photocatalytic performance of the composite. An et al. [30] characterized the TiO₂-MWCNTs nanocomposites photocatalyst prepared with the sol-gel method. Their research aimed to find the degradation efficiency of plastic (polyethylene) by the composite. They observed that composite had an absorption band covering the wide UV-vis range that resulted in increasing the absorption property. Their results show that changing the MWCNTs amount could optimize the degradation efficiency.

Recently, Miandoab et al. investigated the photocatalytic activity of MWCNT/TiO₂ and pseudo-tube TiO₂ degradation of acetaldehyde under visible light and UV-visible. Their results showed that under visible irradiation, the optimum (highest activity) fraction for MWCNT in anatase TiO₂ is 30 wt. %. Qianjie Wang et al. investigated the morphological structures of MWCNT/TiO₂ nanocomposite. They observed that nanocomposite has good absorption in the ultraviolet and visible light regions. Their results proved the efficiency of 83% under ultraviolet ir-

Fig. 4. Photocatalytic mechanism of degradation over the MWCNTs/TiO₂ nanocomposite.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of the difference between CNTs with and without treatment after a complete ALD cycle.

radiation and stability that can be used for wastewater treatment [107].

Huang et al. studied the effect of oxygen contacting functional on the surface of CNT and the rate of growth. They investigated the effect of shell thickness of CNT as a prominent factor to determine the degradation efficiency of methylene blue. The CNT with 22 nm thickness has higher degradation efficiency compared to others after UV irradiation [2]. The schematic of their experimental work is shown in Fig. 5.

Ashkaran et al. [108] studied the CNT/TiO₂ with several methods (simple, heat treatment, and UV illumination). They found that CNT-TiO₂ nanocomposites enhanced the visible light absorption and significantly improved the efficiency of photocatalytic under visible irradiation.

In other research conducted by Akhavan et al. [109], CNT-doped TiO₂ thin films with different TiO₂ contents were prepared, and the results showed the photo-inactivation of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) bacteria. The preparation approach was the sol-gel method in the presence of nitric acid, followed by dip coating to obtain films. The attractive advantages of this method include inexpensive synthesis of TiO₂-CNT hybrids, preventing the addition of extra linker molecules, oxidizing agents, expensive equipment, extended reaction times, and preserving the intrinsic properties of both TiO₂ and the CNTs.

Wang et al. [110] studied the photoactivity of these materials synthesized by the sol-gel method via the conversion of phenol from model aqueous solutions as a probe reaction. A synergistic effect was observed resulting from a strong interaction between TiO₂ nanoparticles and MWCNT. Yen et al. [84] compared the photocatalytic activity for NO oxidation for MWCNT-TiO₂ nanocomposite, which was obtained by sol-gel and the hydrothermal method. The results showed that the former had better photocatalytic activity than that of the latter method.

Nguyen et al. [11] studied SWCNT with TiO₂ nanoparticle. They report that the TiO₂ clusters are coalescence and flexible into larger clusters. Also, they suggested the enhancement of photocatalytic is due to a decrease of recombination ability of electron-hole pairs and an increase in photocatalytic activity of composite because of CNTs presence under

Fig. 6. Schematic of (a) TiO_2 -DWCNTs nanocomposites and (b) flexible DSSC synthetic process.

visible light.

A modified sol-gel route was used by Gao et al. [17] to deposit a uniform TiO_2 film on CNTs to produce a composite structure for enhanced photocatalytic activity. The films were formed through atomic layer deposition (ALD) that were highly conformal films with the capability of atomic-scale thickness control in comparison with sol-gel and other traditional processes such as physical vapor deposition, hydrothermal method, and chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [36].

Dalt et al. [111] designed a TiO_2 /MWCNT for photocatalytic degradation of organic dye (methyl orange dye). They determined an optical characterization by diffuse reflectance and photoluminescence spectroscopies. The heat-treated sample at 500°C has the highest photocatalytic activity under UV radiation.

Most efforts in the field of CNTs deal with aligned nanotube whiskers and single nanotube arrangements [63]. On the other hand, the high potential of TiO_2 as anode material for a new generation of lithium-ion batteries has attracted much attention. Li et al. [87] observed that electron-hole charges of TiO_2 improved by combining with CNT depend on the quality of TiO_2 and CNT interfacial content. Their results show that the thinner TiO_2 layer provides a lower distance for electron transfer to the core of CNT.

Fan et al. [112] investigated the photosynthesis performance of mesoporous TiO_2 -CNT nanocomposite. Their result showed a 3 wt. % CNT nanocomposite at 700°C has the best photoelectric property. Photocurrent density was equal to 0.88 mA cm^{-2} on TiO_2 /CNTs, which is higher than that for the sample without CNTs. Qing et al. [18] studied the electrochemical performance of TiO_2 /CNT in lithium-ion batteries. The CNT/ TiO_2 exhibited 1.5 times greater conductivity than bare TiO_2 nanofiber and 1.6-3 times higher lithium diffusivity. Table 2 lists the recent works about the photocatalytic performance of TiO_2 /CNT nanocomposite.

8.2. Biosensor

Shen et al. [113] used CNT/ TiO_2 for electrochemical biosensing of cancer cells. They reported the significant increase in electrochemical signals on the electrode modified with cancer cells compared to bare carbon nanomaterial. Based on their results, the nanocomposite could accelerate the electron transfer rate and increase detection sensitivity.

8.3. Solar cells

A new generation of solar cells that has attracted much attention is dye-sensitized solar cells (DSCs) due to simple fabrication and high efficiency. Yen et al. [114] synthesized MWCNT- TiO_2 nanocomposites via

a sol-gel method and studied the DSSC performance of the composite. They realized the importance of optimum CNT loading to obtain 4.62% efficiency. Cheng et al. [1] studied the application of TiO_2 /MWCNT in flexible dye-sensitized solar cells. They found that a certain value of composite could decrease the resistance in charge transport that results in an improvement in adsorption of dye. They also suggested that flexible DSSC contains 0.5 wt. % TiO_2 /MWCNT obtain an energy conversion efficiency of 3.89%.

In other work, Abdullah et al. [115] used CNT/ TiO_2 nanocomposite for the fabrication of thin-film at different annealing temperatures. The result showed that the particle was anatase and DSSC with photoanodes annealed at a higher temperature (550°C) had the highest carrier efficiency (95%). Also, the lifetime of photoanodes with higher temperature was increased, and the effective recombination rate was decreased. Moreover, Tetey et al. [116] employed a layer-by-layer assembly using an amphiphilic surfactant for preparation of MWCNT- TiO_2 nanoparticles thin films and reported that the photocatalytic activity of the thin films produced by this method made them suitable for the production of a highly efficient dye-sensitized solar cell. The schematic of TiO_2 -DWCNTs nanocomposites is illustrated in Fig. 6.

8.4. Antibacterial

Abbas et al. [117] investigated the antibacterial synthesis TiO_2 -CNT material. They reported the strong activity of TiO_2 -CNT in the absence of light. They compared different CNT contacting samples for antibacterial activity and some other properties. Their results show that by increasing CNT content, the antibacterial activity increase significantly.

Also, Koli et al. [64] studied the antibacterial activity of CNT/ TiO_2 . They observed that nanocomposites have efficient antibacterial activity under visible light irradiation, whereas TiO_2 nanoparticles did not have any repressive influence on bacteria under visible light. The cytotoxicity study shows that the viability of bare TiO_2 nanoparticles was improved by CNT.

8.5. Other applications

Sanchez et al. investigated the difference of two deposition method, dip coating, and screen printing to obtain a TiO_2 /MWCNT sensor. Their results show that the dip-coated films have no oriented rutile and anatase planes in comparison to screen-printing [118]. Rodriguez et al. [119] investigated the effect of TiO_2 in order to improve the thermal stability of MWCNT in the oxidizing environment. Their results showed that the structure was a changed from anatase to rutile by increasing the tem-

Table 2.Summarize of some photocatalytic performance of TiO₂/CNT nanocomposite with sol-gel method

Light Source	Degraded Component	CNT Content (wt. %)	Performance	Ref.
UV irradiation	methylene blue	19	~2 times higher	[102]
UV light.	NO	-	1.67 times higher	[105]
UV-A irradiation	methylene blue	16	~ 2 times higher	[87]
UV-vis	polyethylene (PE) plastic	20	~ 1.3 times higher	[106]
UV- vis	polyethylene (PE) plastic	20	~ 1.4 times higher	[30]
UV-visible light	Reactive Black 5 dye	20	~ 3 times higher	[3]
UV-visible light and visible light	Acetaldehyde	30	~ 1.8 times higher	[107]
UV- vis	NO oxidation	0-8	~ 1.5 times higher	[84]
UV	MB	0.2	~ 1.5 times higher	[17]
UV- vis	Methyl orange	-	~ 1.83 times higher	[110]
UV and vis	-	50	~ 1.1 and 1.5 times higher	[11]
UV-visible	MB	-	~ 5 times higher	[2]
visible light	Escherichia coli bacteria	-	~ 2.5 times higher	[108]
visible light	Escherichia coli bacteria	20	~ 3 times higher	[109]
UV	dye	-	~ 4 times higher	[111]
UV	Methyl orange	-	~ 1.38 times higher	[112]

perature of calcination. The specimens calcined at a higher temperature (1000 °C) have a higher resistance to oxidation.

9. Conclusions and future insights

This article aimed to review some of the significant works performed about CNT/TiO₂ nanocomposites synthesized via the sol-gel method for various applications. The preparation processes of CNTs were initially presented. In the following, two major types of CNTs, namely SWCNTs and MWCNTs, were studied. CNT/TiO₂ nanocomposite and its preparation processes, especially sol-gel, were reviewed in the next step. Ultimately, the authors introduced several of the major applications about this nanocomposite.

Acknowledgments

The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflicts of interest in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Cheng, J. Wu, Y. Xiao, Y. Chen, H. Yu, Z. Tang, J. Lin, M. Huang, Preparation of titanium dioxide-double-walled carbon nanotubes and its application in flexible dye-sensitized solar cells, *Frontiers of Optoelectronics* 5(2) (2012) 224-230.
- [2] S.-H. Huang, C.-C. Wang, S.-Y. Liao, J.-Y. Gan, T.-P. Perng, CNT/TiO₂ core-shell structures prepared by atomic layer deposition and characterization of their photocatalytic properties, *Thin Solid Films* 616 (2016) 151-159.
- [3] S.B.A. Hamid, T.L. Tan, C.W. Lai, E.M. Samsudin, Multiwalled carbon nano-tube/TiO₂ nanocomposite as a highly active photocatalyst for photodegradation of Reactive Black 5 dye, *Chinese Journal of Catalysis* 35(12) (2014) 2014-2019.
- [4] P. Chand, S. Munjal, T. Aziz, M. Sharma, Unit-12 Carbon and its Compounds, IGNOU 2018.
- [5] T. Gupta, Carbon (C) the Nacre and Its Allotropes, in: T. Gupta (Ed.), *Carbon: The Black, the Gray and the Transparent*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018, pp. 1-45.
- [6] A. Kumar, M.L. Singla, A. Kumar, J.K. Rajput, Fabrication and linearisation of conformable POMANI-Mn3O4 nanocomposite based thermistor for temperature monitoring applications in prosthetic gloves, *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical* 285 (2019) 588-598.

[7] B.I. Kharisov, O.V. Kharissova, Carbon Allotropes in the Environment and Their Toxicity, in: B.I. Kharisov, O.V. Kharissova (Eds.), *Carbon Allotropes: Met-al-Complex Chemistry, Properties and Applications*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019, pp. 639-652.

[8] C. Ozkan, *Handbook of Graphene, Volume 4: Composites*, Wiley 2019.

[9] L.F. Fernandes, G.E. Bruch, A.R. Massensini, F. Frézar, Recent Advances in the Therapeutic and Diagnostic Use of Liposomes and Carbon Nanomaterials in Ischemic Stroke, *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 12(453) (2018).

[10] D. White, M. Chen, C. Xiao, W. Huang, S. Sundararajan, Microtribological behavior of Mo and W nanoparticle/graphene composites, *Wear* 414-415 (2018) 310-316.

[11] M. Nocuń, S. Kwaśny, M. Kwaśny, I. Grelowska, Spectroscopy studies of TiO₂/carbon nanotubes nanocomposite layers synthesized by the sol-gel method, *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1167 (2018) 194-199.

[12] S. Iijima, Helical microtubules of graphitic carbon, *Nature* 354(6348) (1991) 56-58.

[13] Y.M. Chen, X.Y. Yu, Z. Li, U. Paik, X.W. Lou, Hierarchical MoS₂-sub-2<sub>2</sub> tubular structures internally wired by carbon nanotubes as a highly stable anode material for lithium-ion batteries, *Science Advances* 2(7) (2016) e1600021.

[14] M. Ghosh, H. Bovn, M. Moisse, B. Boeckx, R.C. Duca, K. Poels, K. Luyts, E. Putzeys, K. Van Landuydt, J.A. Vanoirbeek, Differences in MWCNT-and SWCNT-induced DNA methylation alterations in association with the nuclear deposition, *Particle and Fibre Technology* 15(1) (2018).

[15] S. Aryal, C.K. Kim, K.-W. Kim, M.S. Khil, H.Y. Kim, Multi-walled carbon nanotubes/TiO₂ composite nanofiber by electrospinning, *Materials Science and Engineering: C* 28(1) (2008) 75-79.

[16] J. Cho, S. Schaab, J.A. Roether, A.R. Boccaccini, Nanostructured carbon nanotube/TiO₂ composite coatings using electrophoretic deposition (EPD), *Journal of Nanoparticle Research* 10(1) (2008) 99-105.

[17] B. Gao, G.Z. Chen, G. Li Puma, Carbon nanotubes/titanium dioxide (CNTs/TiO₂) nanocomposites prepared by conventional and novel surfactant wrapping sol-gel methods exhibiting enhanced photocatalytic activity, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 89(3) (2009) 503-509.

[18] R. Qing, L. Liu, H. Kim, W.M. Sigmund, Electronic Property Dependence of Electrochemical Performance for TiO₂/CNT Core-shell Nanofibers in Lithium Ion Batteries, *Electrochimica Acta* 180 (2015) 295-306.

[19] E.M. Jin, B. Jin, K.-H. Park, H.-B. Gu, G.-C. Park, K.-W. Kim, Electrochemical Characteristics of Lithium Iron Phosphate with Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotube for Lithium Polymer Batteries, *Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology* 8(10) (2008) 5057-5061.

[20] C. Sotowa, G. Origi, M. Takeuchi, Y. Nishimura, K. Takeuchi, I.Y. Jang, Y.J. Kim, T. Hayashi, Y.A. Kim, M. Endo, M.S. Dresselhaus, The Reinforcing Effect of Combined Carbon Nanotubes and Acetylene Blacks on the Positive Electrode of Lithium-Ion Batteries, *ChemSusChem* 1(11) (2008) 911-915.

- [21] R.J. Chen, S. Bangsaruntip, K.A. Drouvalakis, N. Wong Shi Kam, M. Shim, Y. Li, W. Kim, P.J. Utz, H. Dai, Noncovalent functionalization of carbon nanotubes for highly specific electronic biosensors, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 100(9) (2003) 4984.
- [22] G. Gonzalez, C. Albano, V. Herman, I. Boyer, A. Monsalve, J.A. Brito, Nano-composite building blocks of TiO_2 -MWCNTf and ZrO_2 -MWCNTf, *Materials Characterization* 64 (2012) 96-106.
- [23] A.A. White, S.M. Best, I.A. Kinloch, Hydroxyapatite-Carbon Nanotube Composites for Biomedical Applications: A Review, *International Journal of Applied Ceramic Technology* 4(1) (2007) 1-13.
- [24] A. Esmailkhanian, F. Sharifianjazi, A. Abouchenari, A. Rouhani, N. Parvin, M. Irani, Synthesis and Characterization of Natural Nano-hydroxyapatite Derived from Turkey Femur-Bone Waste, *Applied biochemistry and biotechnology* (2019) 1-14.
- [25] S.-H. Lee, S. Pumprueg, B. Moudgil, W. Sigmund, Inactivation of bacterial endospores by photocatalytic nanocomposites, *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* 40(2) (2005) 93-98.
- [26] Y.-J. Xu, Y. Zhuang, X. Fu, New Insight for Enhanced Photocatalytic Activity of TiO_2 by Doping Carbon Nanotubes: A Case Study on Degradation of Benzene and Methyl Orange, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 114(6) (2010) 2669-2676.
- [27] A. Kongkanand, P.V. Kamat, Electron Storage in Single Wall Carbon Nanotubes. Fermi Level Equilibration in Semiconductor-SWCNT Suspensions, *ACS Nano* 1(1) (2007) 13-21.
- [28] R.H. Baughman, A.A. Zakhidov, W.A. de Heer, Carbon Nanotubes--the Route Toward Applications, *Science* 297(5582) (2002) 787.
- [29] K. Woan, G. Pyrgiotakis, W. Sigmund, Photocatalytic Carbon-Nanotube- TiO_2 Composites, *Advanced Materials* 21(21) (2009) 2233-2239.
- [30] Y. An, J. Hou, Z. Liu, B. Peng, Enhanced solid-phase photocatalytic degradation of polyethylene by TiO_2 -MWCNTs nanocomposites, *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 148(1) (2014) 387-394.
- [31] R. Leary, A. Westwood, Carbonaceous nanomaterials for the enhancement of TiO_2 photocatalysis, *Carbon* 49(3) (2011) 741-772.
- [32] C.-Y. Kuo, Convenient dye-degradation mechanisms using UV/ TiO_2 /carbon nanotubes process, *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 163(1) (2009) 239-244.
- [33] L. Song, J. Zhai, P. Du, J. Xiong, F. Ko, A novel bilayer photoanode made of carbon nanotubes incorporated TiO_2 nanorods and Mg^{2+} doped TiO_2 nanorods for flexible dye-sensitized solar cells, *Thin Solid Films* 646 (2018) 44-52.
- [34] A.A. Mejía, L. Béjar, C. Parra, C. Aguilar, A. Medina, E.H. Padilla, S.E. Borjas-García, J.L. Bernal, Characterization of Carbon Nanotubes with TiO_2 by the (CVD) Chemical Vapor Deposition Method, *Microscopy and Microanalysis* 24(S1) (2018) 1094-1095.
- [35] C.-M. Tsai, C.-G. Song, Y.-C. Hung, Y.-G. Jeong, S.H. Oh, J.H. Jeong, H. Kim, H. Huh, J.-W. Yoon, W. Sigmund, Carbon induced phase transformation in electrospun TiO_2 /multiwall carbon nanotube nanofibers, *Ceramics International* 43(4) (2017) 3761-3768.
- [36] H. Yu, X. Quan, S. Chen, H. Zhao, TiO_2 -Multiwalled Carbon Nanotube Heterojunction Arrays and Their Charge Separation Capability, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 111(35) (2007) 12987-12991.
- [37] J. Sun, L. Gao, M. Iwasa, Noncovalent attachment of oxide nanoparticles onto carbon nanotubes using water-in-oil microemulsions, *Chemical Communications* (7) (2004) 832-833.
- [38] F. Sharifianjazi, N. Parvin, M. Tahriri, Synthesis and characteristics of sol-gel bioactive SiO_2 - P_2O_5 - CaO - Ag_2O glasses, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* 476 (2017) 108-113.
- [39] F.S. Jazi, N. Parvin, M. Tahriri, M. Alizadeh, S. Abedini, M. Alizadeh, The relationship between the synthesis and morphology of SnO_2 - Ag_2O nanocomposite, *Synthesis and Reactivity in Inorganic, Metal-Organic, and Nano-Metal Chemistry* 44(5) (2014) 759-764.
- [40] F. Sharifianjazi, N. Parvin, M. Tahriri, Formation of apatite nano-needles on novel gel derived SiO_2 - P_2O_5 - CaO - SrO - Ag_2O bioactive glasses, *Ceramics International* 43(17) (2017) 15214-15220.
- [41] Z. Goudarzi, N. Parvin, F. Sharifianjazi, Formation of hydroxyapatite on surface of SiO_2 - P_2O_5 - CaO - SrO - ZnO bioactive glass synthesized through sol-gel route, *Ceramics International* (2019).
- [42] S. Jurablu, M. Farahmandjou, T.P. Firoozabadi, Multiple-layered structure of obelisk-shaped crystalline nano-ZnO prepared by sol-gel route, *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Physics* 9(4) (2015) 261-266.
- [43] S. Abedini, N. Parvin, P. Ashtari, F. Jazi, Microstructure, strength and CO_2 separation characteristics of α -alumina supported γ -alumina thin film membrane, *Advances in Applied Ceramics* 112(1) (2013) 17-22.
- [44] V. Salimian Rizi, F. Sharifianjazi, H. Jafarikhrami, N. Parvin, L. Saei Fard, M. Irani, A. Esmailkhanian, Sol-gel derived $\text{SnO}_2/\text{Ag}_2\text{O}$ ceramic nanocomposite for H_2 gas sensing applications, *Materials Research Express* 6(11) (2019) 1150g2.
- [45] A. Moghanian, F. Sharifianjazi, P. Abachi, E. Sadeghi, H. Jafarikhrami, A. Sedghi, Production and properties of Cu/TiO_2 nano-composites, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 698 (2017) 518-524.
- [46] M.J. de Andrade, M.D. Lima, C.P. Bergmann, G. de O Ramminger, N.M. Balzaretto, T.M. Costa, M.R. Gallas, Carbon nanotube/silica composites obtained by sol-gel and high-pressure techniques, *Nanotechnology* 19(26) (2008) 265607.
- [47] F.C. Fonseca, G.F. Goya, R.F. Jardim, N.L.V. Carreño, E. Longo, E.R. Leite, R. Muccillo, Magnetic properties of $\text{Ni}:\text{SiO}_2$ nanocomposites synthesized by a modified sol-gel method, *Applied Physics A* 76(4) (2003) 621-623.
- [48] Y. Zhang, Y. Shen, D. Han, Z. Wang, J. Song, L. Niu, Reinforcement of silica with single-walled carbon nanotubes through covalent functionalization, *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 16(47) (2006) 4592-4597.
- [49] C. Zheng, X. Zhen, M. Feng, H.-b. Zhan, Composition and structure evolution of carbon nanotube/silica xerogel composites during the process of laser irradiation, *Guang Pu Xue Yu Guang Pu Fen Xi* 26(10) (2006) 1794-1797.
- [50] C. Zheng, H.-b. Zhan, W.-z. Chen, Study on structure and spectral properties of carbon nanotubes doped silica gel glass composites, *Guang Pu Xue Yu Guang Pu Fen Xi* 26(4) (2006) 694-697.
- [51] L. Berguiga, J. Bellessa, F. Vocanson, E. Bernstein, J.C. Plenet, Carbon nanotube silica glass composites in thin films by the sol-gel technique, *Optical Materials* 28(3) (2006) 167-171.
- [52] J. Ning, J. Zhang, Y. Pan, J. Guo, Surfactants assisted processing of carbon nanotube-reinforced SiO_2 matrix composites, *Ceramics International* 30(1) (2004) 63-67.
- [53] K. Gong, M. Zhang, Y. Yan, L. Su, L. Mao, S. Xiong, Y. Chen, Sol-Gel-Derived Ceramic-Carbon Nanotube Nanocomposite Electrodes: Tunable Electrode Dimension and Potential Electrochemical Applications, *Analytical Chemistry* 76(21) (2004) 6500-6505.
- [54] T.M.H. Costa, H.S. Hoffmann, E.V. Benvenuti, V. Stefani, M.R. Gallas, Pressure-induced changes on the optical properties and microstructure of silica-gel matrices doped with rhodamine 6G, *Optical Materials* 27(12) (2005) 1819-1824.
- [55] T.M.H. Costa, V. Stefani, N.M. Balzaretto, M.R. Gallas, J.A.H. Da Jornada, High-Pressure Entrapment of Rhodamine 6G into a Silica Matrix, *Molecular Crystals and Liquid Crystals* 374(1) (2002) 201-206.
- [56] M.J. de Andrade, M.D. Lima, C.P. Bergmann, G.d.O. Ramminger, N.M. Balzaretto, T.M.H. Costa, M.R. Gallas, Carbon nanotube/silica composites obtained by sol-gel and high-pressure techniques, *Nanotechnology* 19(26) (2008) 265607.
- [57] M. Pohl, H. Kurig, I. Tallo, A. Jänes, E. Lust, Novel sol-gel synthesis route of carbide-derived carbon composites for very high power density supercapacitors, *Chemical Engineering Journal* 320 (2017) 576-587.
- [58] M. Sharma, K. Behl, S. Nigam, M. Joshi, TiO_2 -GO nanocomposite for photocatalysis and environmental applications: A green synthesis approach, *Vacuum* 156 (2018) 434-439.
- [59] N. Saijaiou, P. Kajitvichyanukul, A. Watcharenwong, Preparation of Visible Light Responsive Photocatalyst from Titanium Dioxide Nanotubes Modified with Antimony Trisulfide, *Key Engineering Materials* 792 (2019) 98-103.
- [60] X. Zhang, Y. Wang, B. Liu, Y. Sang, H. Liu, Heterostructures construction on TiO_2 nanobelts: A powerful tool for building high-performance photocatalysts, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 202 (2017) 620-641.
- [61] J. Tian, Z. Zhao, A. Kumar, R.I. Boughton, H. Liu, Recent progress in design, synthesis, and applications of one-dimensional TiO_2 nanostructured surface heterostructures: a review, *Chemical Society Reviews* 43(20) (2014) 6920-6937.
- [62] J. Tian, X. Hu, N. Wei, Y. Zhou, X. Xu, H. Cui, H. Liu, $\text{RuO}_2/\text{TiO}_2$ nanobelt heterostructures with enhanced photocatalytic activity and gas-phase selective oxidation of benzyl alcohol, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 151 (2016) 7-13.
- [63] V.G. Gavalas, R. Andrews, D. Bhattacharyya, L.G. Bachas, Carbon Nanotube Sol-Gel Composite Materials, *Nano Letters* 1(12) (2001) 719-721.
- [64] V.B. Koli, A.G. Dhodamani, S.D. Delekar, S.H. Pawar, In situ sol-gel synthesis of anatase TiO_2 -MWCNTs nanocomposites and their photocatalytic applications, *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry* 333 (2017) 40-48.
- [65] L. Yang, D. He, Q. Cai, C.A. Grimes, Fabrication and Catalytic Properties of Co-Ag-Pt Nanoparticle-Decorated Titania Nanotube Arrays, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 111(23) (2007) 8214-8217.
- [66] L. Yang, W. Yang, Q. Cai, Well-Dispersed PtAu Nanoparticles Loaded into Anodic Titania Nanotubes: A High Antipoison and Stable Catalyst System for Methanol Oxidation in Alkaline Media, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 111(44) (2007) 16613-16617.
- [67] E. Antolini, Photo-assisted methanol oxidation on Pt- TiO_2 catalysts for di-

- rect methanol fuel cells: A short review, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 237 (2018) 491-503.
- [68] L. Deng, G. Dong, Y. Zhang, D. Li, T. Lu, Y. Chen, H. Yuan, Y. Chen, Ly-sine-modified TiO₂ nanotube array for optimizing bioelectricity generation in mi-cro-bial fuel cells, *Electrochimica Acta* 300 (2019) 163-170.
- [69] S. Mao, H. Zhou, S. Wu, J. Yang, Z. Li, X. Wei, X. Wang, Z. Wang, J. Li, High performance hydrogen sensor based on Pd/TiO₂ composite film, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 43(50) (2018) 22727-22732.
- [70] Z. Li, Z. Yao, A.A. Haidry, T. Plecenik, L. Xie, L. Sun, Q. Fatima, Resistive-type hydrogen gas sensor based on TiO₂: A review, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 43(45) (2018) 21114-21132.
- [71] S. Ratan, C. Kumar, A. Kumar, D.K. Jarwal, A.K. Mishra, S. Jit, Fabrication and Characterization of Titanium Dioxide Based Pd/TiO₂/Si MOS Sensor for Hydrogen Gas, *IEEE Sensors Journal* 18(10) (2018) 3952-3959.
- [72] S. Mohd Chachuli, M. Hamidon, M. Mamat, M. Ertugrul, N. Abdullah, A Hydrogen Gas Sensor Based on TiO₂ Nanoparticles on Alumina Substrate, *Sensors* 18(8) (2018) 2483.
- [73] H.-F. Cui, W.-W. Wu, M.-M. Li, X. Song, Y. Lv, T.-T. Zhang, A highly stable acetylcholinesterase biosensor based on chitosan-TiO₂-graphene nanocomposites for detection of organophosphate pesticides, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* 99 (2018) 223-229.
- [74] B. Çakıroğlu, M. Özacar, A self-powered photoelectrochemical glucose bio-sensor based on supercapacitor Co₃O₄-CNT hybrid on TiO₂, *Biosensors and Bio-electronics* 119 (2018) 34-41.
- [75] X. Wu, H. Zhang, K. Huang, Y. Zeng, Z. Zhu, Rose petal and P123 dual-tem-plated macro-mesoporous TiO₂ for a hydrogen peroxide biosensor, *Bio-electro-chemistry* 120 (2018) 150-156.
- [76] J. Tian, Y. Li, J. Dong, M. Huang, J. Lu, Photoelectrochemical TiO₂ nanotube arrays biosensor for asulam determination based on in-situ generation of quantum dots, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* 110 (2018) 1-7.
- [77] H. Wang, H. Yin, H. Huang, K. Li, Y. Zhou, G.I.N. Waterhouse, H. Lin, S. Ai, Dual-signal amplified photoelectrochemical biosensor for detection of N6-meth-yladenosine based on BiVO₄/110-TiO₂ heterojunction, Ag⁺-mediated cytosine pairs, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* 108 (2018) 89-96.
- [78] H. Liang, Q. Meng, X. Wang, H. Zhang, J. Wang, Nanoplasmonically En-gineered Interfaces on Amorphous TiO₂ for Highly Efficient Photocatalysis in Hydro-gen Evolution, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 10(16) (2018) 14145-14152.
- [79] J.-C. Wang, H.-H. Lou, Z.-H. Xu, C.-X. Cui, Z.-J. Li, K. Jiang, Y.-P. Zhang, L.-B. Qu, W. Shi, Natural sunlight driven highly efficient photocatalysis for simul-taneous degradation of rhodamine B and methyl orange using I/C codoped TiO₂ photocatalyst, *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 360 (2018) 356-363.
- [80] S. Zhou, N. Bao, Q. Zhang, X. Jie, Y. Jin, Engineering hierarchical porous oxygen-deficient TiO₂ fibers decorated with BiOCl nanosheets for efficient photo-catalysis, *Applied Surface Science* 471 (2019) 96-107.
- [81] W. Wang, P. Serp, P. Kalck, J.L. Faria, Visible light photodegradation of phen-ol on MWNT-TiO₂ composite catalysts prepared by a modified sol-gel method, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* 235(1) (2005) 194-199.
- [82] Y. Ou, J. Lin, S. Fang, D. Liao, MWNT-TiO₂:Ni composite catalyst: A new class of catalyst for photocatalytic H₂ evolution from water under visible light illu-mination, *Chemical Physics Letters* 429(1) (2006) 199-203.
- [83] K. Byrappa, A.S. Dayananda, C.P. Sajan, B. Basavalingu, M.B. Shayan, K. Soga, M. Yoshimura, Hydrothermal preparation of ZnO:CNT and TiO₂:CNT com-posites and their photocatalytic applications, *Journal of Materials Science* 43(7) (2008) 2348-2355.
- [84] C.-Y. Yen, Y.-F. Lin, C.-H. Hung, Y.-H. Tseng, C.-C.M. Ma, M.-C. Chang, H. Shao, The effects of synthesis procedures on the morphology and photocatalytic activity of multi-walled carbon nanotubes/TiO₂ nanocomposites, *Nanotechnology* 19(4) (2008) 045604.
- [85] F.C. Moraes, M.F. Cabral, L.H. Mascaro, S.A.S. Machado, The electro-chemi-cal effect of acid functionalisation of carbon nanotubes to be used in sensors devel-opment, *Surface Science* 605(3) (2011) 435-440.
- [86] C.-H. Wu, C.-Y. Kuo, S.-T. Chen, Synergistic effects between TiO₂ and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in a TiO₂/CNTs system under visible light irradiation, *Envi-ron-mental Technology* 34(17) (2013) 2513-2519.
- [87] Z. Li, B. Gao, G.Z. Chen, R. Mokaya, S. Sotiropoulos, G.L. Puma, Carbon nanotube/titanium dioxide (CNT/TiO₂) core-shell nanocomposites with tailored shell thickness, CNT content and photocatalytic/photoelectrocatalytic properties, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 110 (2011) 50-57.
- [88] W. Wang, P. Serp, P. Kalck, J.L. Faria, Photocatalytic degradation of phenol on MWNT and titania composite catalysts prepared by a modified sol-gel method, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 56(4) (2005) 305-312.
- [89] Y. Yu, J.C. Yu, C.-Y. Chan, Y.-K. Che, J.-C. Zhao, L. Ding, W.-K. Ge, P.-K. Wong, Enhancement of adsorption and photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ by using carbon nanotubes for the treatment of azo dye, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 61(1) (2005) 1-11.
- [90] K.R. Reddy, M.S. Jyothi, A.V. Raghu, V. Sadhu, S. Naveen, T.M. Aminabha-vi, Nanocarbons-Supported and Polymers-Supported Titanium Dioxide Nano-struc-tures as Efficient Photocatalysts for Remediation of Contaminated Waste-water and Hydrogen Production, in: Inamuddin, A.M. Asiri, E. Lichtfouse (Eds.), *Nano-photocatalysis and Environmental Applications : Detoxification and Disin-fection*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020, pp. 139-169.
- [91] X.-H. Xia, Z.-J. Jia, Y. Yu, Y. Liang, Z. Wang, L.-L. Ma, Preparation of multi-walled carbon nanotube supported TiO₂ and its photocatalytic activity in the re-duc-tion of CO₂ with H₂O, *Carbon* 45(4) (2007) 717-721.
- [92] M. Nasr, C. Eid, R. Habchi, P. Miele, M. Bechelany, Recent Progress on Ti-tanium Dioxide Nanomaterials for Photocatalytic Applications, *ChemSusChem* 11(18) (2018) 3023-3047.
- [93] B. Ahmmad, Y. Kusumoto, S. Somekawa, M. Ikeda, Carbon nanotubes syn-ergistically enhance photocatalytic activity of TiO₂, *Catalysis Communications* 9(6) (2008) 1410-1413.
- [94] D. Zhang, X. Ma, H. Zhang, Y. Liao, Q. Xiang, Enhanced photocatalytic hy-drogen evolution activity of carbon and nitrogen self-doped TiO₂ hollow sphere with the creation of oxygen vacancy and Ti³⁺, *Materials Today Energy* 10 (2018) 132-140.
- [95] M. Sánchez, R. Guirado, M.E. Rincón, Multiwalled carbon nanotubes em-bed-ded in sol-gel derived TiO₂ matrices and their use as room temperature gas sensors, *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics* 18(11) (2007) 1131-1136.
- [96] T.Y. Lee, P.S. Alegaonkar, J.-B. Yoo, Fabrication of dye sensitized solar cell using TiO₂ coated carbon nanotubes, *Thin Solid Films* 515(12) (2007) 5131-5135.
- [97] H.M. Ghartavol, M.R. Mohammadi, A. Afshar, Y. Li, On the assessment of incorporation of CNT-TiO₂ core-shell structures into nanoparticle TiO₂ photo-an-odes in dye-sensitized solar cells, *Photochemical & Photobiological Sciences* 18(7) (2019) 1840-1850.
- [98] S.M. Sakali, M.H. Khanmirzaei, S.C. Lu, S. Ramesh, K. Ramesh, Investi-gation on gel polymer electrolyte-based dye-sensitized solar cells using carbon nano-tube, *Ionics* 25(1) (2019) 319-325.
- [99] D. Tasis, N. Tagmatarchis, A. Bianco, M. Prato, Chemistry of Carbon Nano-tubes, *Chemical Reviews* 106(3) (2006) 1105-1136.
- [100] D. Eder, Carbon Nanotube-Inorganic Hybrids, *Chemical Reviews* 110(3) (2010) 1348-1385.
- [101] C.G. Silva, J.L. Faria, Photocatalytic oxidation of benzene derivatives in aqueous suspensions: Synergic effect induced by the introduction of carbon nano-tubes in a TiO₂ matrix, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 101(1) (2010) 81-89.
- [102] M.-I. Chen, F.-j. Zhang, W.-c. Oh, Synthesis, characterization, and photo-catalytic analysis of CNT/TiO₂ composites derived from MWCNTs and titanium sources, *New Carbon Materials* 24(2) (2009) 159-166.
- [103] J. Ge, Y. Zhang, Y.-J. Heo, S.-J. Park, Advanced Design and Synthesis of Composite Photocatalysts for the Remediation of Wastewater: A Review, *Catalysts* 9 (2019) 122.
- [104] S. Muduli, W. Lee, V. Dhas, S. Mujawar, M. Dubey, K. Vijayamohan, S.-H. Han, S. Ogale, Enhanced Conversion Efficiency in Dye-Sensitized Solar Cells Based on Hydrothermally Synthesized TiO₂-MWCNT Nanocomposites, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 1(9) (2009) 2030-2035.
- [105] Y.-H. Tseng, C.-Y. Yen, M.-Y. Yen, C.-C. Ma, Effects of the acid pretreated multi-walled carbon nanotubes on the photocatalytic capacity of TiO₂/multi-walled carbon nanotubes nanocomposites, *Micro & Nano Letters* 5(1) (2010) 1-6.
- [106] M.-Q. Yang, N. Zhang, Y.-J. Xu, Synthesis of fullerene-, carbon nano-tube-, and graphene-TiO₂ nanocomposite photocatalysts for selective oxidation: a com-parative study, *ACS applied materials & interfaces* 5(3) (2013) 1156-1164.
- [107] E. Soroodan Miandoab, S. Fatemi, Upgrading TiO₂ photoactivity under vis-ible light by synthesis of MWCNT/TiO₂ nanocomposite, *International Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology* 11(1) (2015) 1-12.
- [108] A.A. Ashkarran, M. Fakhari, M. Mahmoudi, Synthesis of a solar photo and bioactive CNT-TiO₂ nanocatalyst, *RSC Advances* 3(40) (2013) 18529-18536.
- [109] O. Akhavan, R. Azimirad, S. Safa, M. Larijani, Visible light photo-induced antibacterial activity of CNT-doped TiO₂ thin films with various CNT contents, *Journal of Materials Chemistry* 20(35) (2010) 7386-7392.
- [110] Q. Wang, Y. Wang, B. Duan, M. Zhang, Modified sol-gel synthesis of carbon nanotubes supported titania composites with enhanced visible light induced photo-catalytic activity, *Journal of Nanomaterials* 2016 (2016) 1.
- [111] S. Da Dalt, A.K. Alves, F.A. Berutti, C.P. Bergmann, Designing of TiO₂/MWCNT Nanocomposites for Photocatalytic Degradation of Organic Dye, Par-

Science and Technology 33(3) (2015) 308-313.

[112] X. Fan, T. Wang, Y. Guo, H. Gong, H. Xue, H. Guo, B. Gao, J. He, Synthesis of ordered mesoporous TiO₂-Carbon-CNTs nanocomposite and its efficient photo-electrocatalytic methanol oxidation performance, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials* 240 (2017) 1-8.

[113] Q. Shen, S.-K. You, S.-G. Park, H. Jiang, D. Guo, B. Chen, X. Wang, Electrochemical Biosensing for Cancer Cells Based on TiO₂/CNT Nanocomposites Modified Electrodes, *Electroanalysis* 20(23) (2008) 2526-2530.

[114] C.-Y. Yen, Y.-F. Lin, S.-H. Liao, C.-C. Weng, C.-C. Huang, Y.-H. Hsiao, C.-C.M. Ma, M.-C. Chang, H. Shao, M.-C. Tsai, Preparation and properties of a carbon nanotube-based nanocomposite photoanode for dye-sensitized solar cells, *Nanotechnology* 19(37) (2008) 375305.

[115] H. Abdullah, M.Z. Razali, S. Shaari, M.R. Taha, Enhancement of dye-sensitized solar cell efficiency using carbon nanotube/TiO₂ nanocomposite thin films fabricated at various annealing temperatures, *Electronic Materials Letters* 10(3)

(2014) 611-619.

[116] K.E. Tettey, M.Q. Yee, D. Lee, Photocatalytic and Conductive MWCNT/TiO₂ Nanocomposite Thin Films, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 2(9) (2010) 2646-2652.

[117] N. Abbas, G.N. Shao, M.S. Haider, S.M. Imran, S.S. Park, S.-J. Jeon, H.T. Kim, Inexpensive sol-gel synthesis of multiwalled carbon nanotube-TiO₂ hybrids for high performance antibacterial materials, *Materials Science and Engineering: C* 68 (2016) 780-788.

[118] M. Sánchez, M. Rincón, Sensor response of sol-gel multiwalled carbon nanotubes-TiO₂ composites deposited by screen-printing and dip-coating techniques, *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 140(1) (2009) 17-23.

[119] L.A.A. Rodríguez, M. Pianassola, D.N. Travessa, Production of TiO₂ coated multiwall carbon nanotubes by the sol-gel technique, *Materials research* 20 (2017) 96-103.